

Evaluations of Wind Speed Distribution and Wind Power Potential over Ethiopia (A case of Ambo)

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ABSTRACT

Renewable energy sources gained significant attention; due to several climate changes caused by greenhouse gases and to increasing need for clean energy sources, wind energy is one of the most promising energy sources in the future. This study investigates the wind power potential of Ambo area, a city located in West Shewa Zone of Oromia Region, West of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia using real wind speed data. A 6-year wind speed data (2010-2015) measured at 10 m height was obtained from the National Meteorological Agency of Ethiopia and statistically analysed. The result of the study showed that Ambo has an average wind speed of 3.2 m/s at 10 m height (5.0 m/s and 6.2 m/s at extrapolated 30 and 50 m heights, respectively) with maximum value of 4.5 m/s in February and the lowest wind speed was recorded during the months of June and July (2.0 m/s for each month). The corresponding mean wind power density at 10 m, 30 m and 50 m heights are 26.0, 97.3 and 179.2 W/m², respectively, for the whole year and this makes the site to fall under Class 2 (Marginal) of the International System of Wind Classification. The monthly values of Weibull shape parameter k ranged from 2.19 to 3.20 with an average value of 2.80. While the monthly values of the Weibull scale parameter c were in the range of 2.28-5.02 m/s, with an average value of 3.64 m/s. Weibull probability density function and cumulative frequency showed that the wind speed tends to distribute around the mean value most of the time. It was also concluded that the site studied was not suitable for electric wind application in large-scale. It was found that the wind potential of the region could be adequate for non-grid connected electrical and mechanical applications, such as wind generators, battery charging and water pumping as well as agricultural applications.

Keywords: Weibull Distribution, Wind Potential, Wind Power Density, Wind Speed, Ambo, Ethiopia.

INTRODUCTION

Energy is undoubtedly the driving force at the core of the development of any nation. There is a direct relation between per capita income and energy consumption. The way this energy is produced, supplied and consumed, affects the local and global environment and is therefore a key issue in sustainable development. Due to growing concerns of environment protection, energy security and price of fossil fuels, there is strong interest in renewable energy development such as hydro, wind, solar, geothermal and bioenergy [17].

Ethiopia is one of developing countries in the Eastern Africa and non-oil-producing country with more than 80% of its population live without usable electricity. The largest portion of their primary energy supply is from biomass; and wood is the dominant source of energy for households [16], [46]. The people in rural area of Ethiopia use fire wood for cooking and heating purpose in an unsustainable and inefficient way. Desertification of the land is getting worse and worse due to deforestation and backward agriculture. In addition, indoor air pollution from incomplete combustion has potential health problem to women and children.

The situation clearly highlights the need to exploit all the country's potential energy resources immediately and by any means possible in order to alleviate the problems and provide energy services for the people in need. At the same time, the development of the energy sector would help in the appraisal and development of the industrial economy which is, in its own way, the future goal of the country [22].

When looking into the sources of energy available to the country, hydropower occupies the major share. Unfortunately it is not accessible to most rural areas in the foreseeable future due to limits

in both production

facilities and the distribution system (power lines). In many areas, solar and wind energy are the main locally available energy resources. Due to its geographical location the country enjoys a considerable amount of sunshine for most months of the year. Furthermore, due to the fact that the summer monsoon, tropical easterlies, and local convergence over the Red Sea control the wind regimes, there is significant wind energy, with a varying annual mean speed which decreases from east to west [47], [49].

Representing wind speed probability distribution and the function, mathematically are the main tools used in the wind related literature. In application, Weibull distribution function is the most commonly used. The Weibull two parameter density functions are often used to describe the variation of wind velocity. Wind energy potential is not easily estimated because, it depends on the site characteristics and topography to a large degree, as wind speed are influenced strongly by local topographical features [4],[35],[34],[48]. The assessment of the suitable regions for wind energy utilization and the estimation of the expected power production of wind turbines are a prerequisite for efficient wind turbine sitting under economic, social and environmental constraints [11]. Therefore, accurate wind resource assessment is essential in the choice of a profitable location for harnessing wind power.

In this work, the aim is to establish an accurate assessment of wind energy potential for Ambo, city in Ethiopia, by the application of well assessed methodologies that are recalled within the paper. A six-year (2010-2015) hourly wind data at 10 m height were obtained from the National Meteorological Agency of Ethiopia. A careful

wind resource assessment and viability of adopting the location for wind power generation using wind energy conversion system was done.

2. Previous Studies and Wind Energy Status in Ethiopia

2.1. Previous Studies

Several studies have been done regarding the wind energy potential in Ethiopia. From these studies those done by Wolde-Ghiorgis (1988)[47], and Drake and Mulugetta (1996)[49] have given significant results regarding the wind energy potential in the country by identifying the wind regimes in several areas. However, the data used in these studies is relatively old; the most recent data used in the first study [47] is from 1968-1973 and was recorded only three times a day, at 6:00, 12:00, and 18:00. The remaining data used was also recorded three times a day at 8:00, 14:00 and 19:00 during the period 1937 – 1940. Data used in the second study [49] was collected during the period 1979-1990 at 60 different locations across the country and recordings were made, according to the author, 4 to 7 times per day at a height of 2 m. In addition to these studies Getachew (2009)[22] had conducted wind energy surveys on four sites in the country (Addis Ababa, Mekele, Nazret and Debrezeit). Data used in this study was relatively recent, collected during the period 2000-2003 and was recorded five times a day, at 6:00, 9:00, 12:00, 15:00, and 18:00, at a height of 10 meters.

Unlike the previous studies, this study focuses on one specific location called Ambo, which is not studied by any of the previous studies, situated in West Shewa Zones of Oromia region, Ethiopia.

2.2. Wind Energy Status in Ethiopia

Ethiopia has exploitable reserve of 10 GW wind energy with an average speed of 3.5 – 5.5 m/s, flowing for 6 hours/day[49], [13],[12],[27],[14],[15]. Wind energy in Ethiopian is used mainly for electricity generation and water pumping[14]. Wind energy, so far has been used in water pumping applications in some regions of Rift Valley. [4].

For electricity generation, there are three wind farms connected to the electricity grid in the country; one with a capacity of 120 MW in Ashegoda near Mekele city, consisting of 52 wind turbines (Diameter =74 m) of 1.670MW each and 30 wind turbines (Diameter =62 m) of 1.0 MW each . The other has a capacity of 51 MW in Adama wind farm I (near Adama city), consisting of 34 wind turbines of 1.5MW each. The third one has a capacity of 153 MW in Adama wind farm II (near Adama city), making it the largest wind farm in sub-Saharan Africa to date. This wind farm consisting of 102 wind turbines of 1.5 MW each Wind energy application in Ethiopia has been limited so far. Utility scale wind energy projects of Ayesb, Debre Berhan and Messebo are also examples of large scale development [15], [2], [10].

3. Methodology

3.1. Ethiopian Climate and Site Description

Ethiopia lies in the Horn of Africa within latitude 8°00north and longitude 38°00east. It is a country with a total area of 1,127,127 km² including 7,444 km² of water. The terrain is mainly high plateau with mountain ranges divided by The Great Rift Valley. The elevation generally ranges between 1,500 and 3,000 meters above sea level with extremities of 125 m below sea level in the Denakil Depression and 4,620 m above sea level at Ras Dashen. Ambo is a spa town, located in Western Shewa Zone of the Oromia Region, West of Addis Ababa, this town has a latitude and longitude of 8.9830N 37.8500E and an elevation of 2101 meters.

3.2. Wind Speed Data Used in this Study

The estimation of wind energy potential is based on the knowledge

of wind regimes on the considered territory. The accuracy of this phase is crucial as the provided power is proportional to the cube of wind speed[9]. In this work, the assessment of Ambo wind potential has been carried out. The data on wind speed for this study are taken from Ethiopian National Meteorological Agency (NMA). Wind speed was collected every 3 hours at a 10 m height during 6 years from 2010 to 2015. The reason for performing wind measurements at 10 m height was primarily for a purpose of aviation [47], [30], where it has been agreed that this should be the standard meteorological reference height in order to achieve representative recording of the wind potential of the area. Furthermore, the wind speed at higher heights could be calculated using the power law[1], [24]. According to the requirements for wind energy assessment, representative year can be used to estimate the wind energy resource potential. The data have been used to evaluate the annual frequency of wind speed, the vertical (extrapolated) profile of the wind speed and the assessment of potential wind power.

3.3 Mathematical Models

3.3.1 Measured average wind speed and standard deviation

The monthly average wind speed v_{av} and the standard deviation σ of the time-series of measured hourly wind speed data are determined using equation (1) and (2), respectively [19],[7],[20],[50],[8]:

$$v_{av} = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N v_i \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (v_i - v_m)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Where: v_m , average wind speed, m/s; σ , standard deviation of the observed data, m/s; v_i , Daily wind speed, m/s; N, number of measured daily wind speed data.

3.3.2 Wind Speed Extrapolation

In most locations wind speed varies considerably with height, a phenomenon known as wind shear. Wind speeds used for this paper are collected at 10 m height. However, for the purpose of installation of a wind energy conversion system (WECS), it is necessary for the wind speed to be estimated at the respective turbine hub heights. Power law method is most commonly used to adjust wind velocity at a reference level to another. It is expressed as [35], [34], [9], [25],[37],[51],[26],[5],[40],[23],[32]:

$$\frac{V}{V_o} = \left(\frac{H}{H_o} \right)^\alpha \quad (3)$$

where ‘V’ is the wind speed at the required height ‘H’, ‘V_o’ is wind speed at the reference height ‘H_o’, and ‘ α ’ is ground surface friction coefficient which lies in the range 0.05-0.5. A value of 0.4 was chosen in this paper for extrapolation at various heights because the location of the site where the anemometer is cited to measure the wind speed falls into surface topology that comprises of Cities with tall building. The estimated wind speeds were then used to quantify approximately how much more power could be harnessed at different hub heights on the site.

3.3.3 Frequency Distribution of Wind Speed

Statistical analysis can be used to determine the wind energy

potential of a given site and to estimate the wind energy output at this site. Depending on local climate conditions, the landscape and its surface, the statistical distribution of wind speeds varies from place to place. Weibull distribution is commonly used to describe the wind speed distribution of a typical site.[4],[35],[34],[48],[9],[24],[25],[37],[26],[40],[23],[32],[36].

3.3.3.1 Weibull distribution function

The most common distribution functions are the Rayleigh and Weibull distribution functions which are used to illustrate the wind speed data. The Weibull distribution has been playing an important role to model and predict wind power and distributions. Weibull distribution is very flexible and easy to apply. The simplest form of Weibull distribution has two parameters: the parameter 'k' (known as scale parameter, dimensionless) and 'c' the scale parameter, c has dimension of velocity. Weibull distribution can be characterized by its probability density function (PDF) and cumulative distribution function (CDF) [7],[20],[50],[38],[39],[8],[6],[2],[29],[45],[31].

Probability Density Function (PDF): Weibull Probability density function has been used by a number of researchers for modeling and predicting wind energy. The wind speed is used as a continuous random variable of the distribution. The mathematical form of PDF is:

$$f(v) = \left(\frac{k}{c}\right) * \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^{k-1} * \exp\left[-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^k\right] \quad (k > 0, v > 0, c > 1) \quad (4)$$

where $f(v)$, is the probability of observing wind speed v , k , is the dimensionless Weibull shape parameter and c , is the Weibull scale parameter with unit equals to the wind speed unit. The Weibull parameters, k and c , characterize the wind potential of the sites under study. The shape parameter 'k' helps in finding how frequently wind speeds are close to some measured speed. The value of k represents variation in average wind speed in a given sample; higher the value of k more the stability in wind speed. The scale parameter (c) is an indicator of wind potential of a place. The large value of 'c' is an indication of high wind power

Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF): The cumulative Weibull distribution $F(v)$ gives the probability of the wind speed exceeding the value v , it is expressed as[24],[37]:

$$F(v) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^k\right] \quad (5)$$

3.3.3.2 Methods to estimate Weibull parameters

The parameters of Weibull distribution's parameter (k and c) can be found by a number of ways. Some of them are mentioned here.

Maximum Likelihood Method (MLM): MLM was suggested by Steven et al. [31]. It adopts an iterative procedure for determination of parameters, k and c . These parameters are found by the equations(6a) and (6b)[20],[39],[2],[29],[31],[33],[44],[3],[18]:

$$k = \left[\frac{\sum_i^n v_i^k * \ln(v_i)}{\sum_i^n v_i^k} - \frac{\sum_i^n \ln(v_i)}{n} \right]^{-1} \quad (6a)$$

$$C = \frac{\sum_i^n v_i^k}{n} \quad (6b)$$

A special care must be taken in estimating Weibull parameters through MLM for wind data that includes zero wind speed. The reason is clear from the shape parameter equation that involves logarithm; Logarithm of zero makes the calculation indeterminate. An initial value of $k = 2$ is suitable to start the iteration.

Modified Maximum Likelihood Method (MMLM): The modified maximum likelihood method employs frequency distribution, i.e. the data should be in Weibull distribution format [17], like MLM, it is also an iterative method. Equations (7a) and (7b) are used to calculate Weibull parameters, k and c [20],[39],[33],[44],[3],[18],[43]

$$k = \left[\frac{\sum_i^n v_i^k * \ln(v_i) * f(v_i)}{\sum_i^n v_i^k * f(v_i)} - \frac{\sum_i^n \ln(v_i) * f(v_i)}{f(v \geq 0)} \right]^{-1} \quad (7a)$$

$$C = \frac{\sum_i^n v_i^k * f(v_i)}{f(v \geq 0)} \quad (7b)$$

Methods of Moments (MoM): It is considered as an alternative to MLM. The Weibull factors k and C for the Moment Method (MM) are estimated from the average wind speed v_{av} and standard deviation σ of wind data. The MoM method is solved through numerical iterations by the following equations [3][39],[2]:

$$\bar{v} = C * \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right) \quad (8a)$$

$$\sigma = C * \left[\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right) - \Gamma^2\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right) \right]^{1/2} \quad (8b)$$

Empirical Method (EM): It is considered as a special case of the moment method, uses standard deviation and mean wind speed for determining Weibull parameters. K and c parameters are evaluated by equation (9a) and (9b)[50],[38],[39],[33],[44],[3],[18]:

$$k = \left(\frac{\sigma}{v}\right)^{-1.086} \quad (9a)$$

$$\bar{v} = C * \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right) \quad (9b)$$

Energy Pattern Factor Method (EPF): EPM, also known as power density method, is simple and easy to implement. It uses average of wind speed cubes and cube of average wind speed. The shape factor is determined directly from energy pattern factor (Epf). The equations for finding scale parameters are the same as those used for MoM and EM. These equations are given below[39],[33],[44],[3],[18]:

$$E_{pf} = \frac{\bar{V}^3}{(\bar{V})^3} \quad (10a)$$

$$k = 1 + \frac{3.69}{(E_{pf})^2} \quad (10b)$$

$$\bar{v} = C * \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right) \quad (10c)$$

Graphical Method: Least-squares regression method: In this method, the cumulative distribution function is transformed into a linear form, adopting logarithmic scales [20],[39],[6],

[33],[44],[3]. Then, the expression for the cumulative distribution of wind velocity can be rewritten as

$$1 - F(v) = \exp\left[-\left(\frac{v}{C}\right)^k\right] \quad (11a)$$

Taking the logarithm twice, we get

$$\ln\{-\ln[1 - F(V_i)]\} = k \ln(v_i) - k \ln C \quad (11b)$$

Table 1: A summary of statistical parameters in the accuracy evaluation of model

Statistical test	Description	Mathematical expression in terms of measured (y_i) and estimated (x_i) values.	Statistics for best model performance
RMSE	Provides information on the short-term performance of the correlations. A few large errors in the sum can produce a significant increase in RMSE.	$RMSE = \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=a}^N (y_i - x_i)^2 \right]^{1/2}$	Low RMSE (close to zero)
MPE	Provides long-term performance of the examined regression equations. An overall measure of forecast bias.	$MPE(\%) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\frac{x_i - y_i}{y_i} \right] * 100$	Between -10% & +10% is considered acceptable.

3.1.2. Wind Power Calculation

For any wind stream with speed v (m/s), of cross-sectional area A (m^2), and air density ($\rho=1.225\text{kg/m}^3$) the theoretical power (P) that is available can be obtained from [40],[23],[32]

$$P = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 \quad (\text{Watts}) \quad (12)$$

The total wind power density, P/A is the total available power per unit area, which is given by

$$\frac{P}{A} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho \frac{1}{n} \sum v_i^3 \right) \quad (13)$$

where: n is the number of days in a month. Before calculating the average wind power density, v_i^3 of each day for the extrapolated height at 50 m was calculated and the values are summed ($\sum v_i^3$),

and then divided by the number of days in a month $\frac{1}{n} (\sum v_i^3)$.

3.1.3. Wind Energy Calculation

The electric energy produced by a turbine over the year is given by the following relationship [31]:

$$E = \left[\frac{1}{2} C_p \rho A \int v^3 f(v) dv \right] * T \quad (14)$$

where: C_p is the power coefficient and T is the time period (For the annual wind energy estimation, $T=8,760$ hours is used). The actual power available to drive a practical wind turbine is much less than the theoretical maximum value. A practical wind machine, experiences air drag on the blades and friction of the air on the blades causing heat losses. In addition, the rotation of the rotor causes swirling of the air, which reduces the torque imparted to the blade [49]. The net effect of the various losses is incorporated into a parameter called the power coefficient or coefficient of

Plotting the above relationship with $\ln(v)$ along the x-axis and $\ln\{-\ln[1 - F(V_i)]\}$ along the y-axis, nearly a straight line is obtained. From Eq. (14), k gives the slope of this line and represents the intercept.

3.1.1.1. Performance of the Weibull parameters

There are many parameters which used to evaluate the performance of the Weibull methods. Here the statistical parameters like the root mean square error (RMSE) and Mean percentage error (MPE) were utilized (Table 1).

performance C_p (dimensionless variable). For practical wind turbines its value is usually in the range $0 \leq C_p \leq 0.4$. The power coefficient C_p has a value that depends on the wind velocity, turbine rotational velocity and turbine blade parameters [26], [28].

The available mean wind power density, P_d , and the overall wind energy density, E_d , of a wind turbine for a period of time T will be calculated as equation (15)[42], [11]:

$$P_d = \frac{P}{A} = \frac{1}{2} \rho v^3 = 0.6125 v^3 \quad (\text{Watts} / m^2) \quad (15)$$

$$E_d = \frac{E}{A} = P_d T \quad (\text{Wh} / m^2)$$

4. Results and Discussion

In this study, wind speed data for Ambo, over six-year period from 2010 to 2015 were analyzed. Based on these data, calculations were then made to obtain the average wind speed at anemometric height and extrapolated heights, the Weibull distribution parameters in terms of k and c , average wind power and energy density. The main results obtained from the present study can be summarized as follows.

4.1. Wind Resource Data Analysis

Future and available wind potential is very important to build of wind energy conversion system. For this reason estimation parameter results of distribution are studied monthly. In this paper, estimation of monthly and annual parameters for Ambo area was evaluated by using hourly wind speed data between 2010 and 2015. The monthly average wind speed values v_{av} and standard deviations σ for the entire years and their average were calculated by using the equations (1) and (2), respectively (Table 2). For the six years, the average annual wind speed is 3.2 m/s. The minimum wind speed for all the six years is 2.0 m/s, which occurred in the months of June and July, while the maximum was 4.5 m/s in February

Table 1: Monthly average wind speeds and standard deviations for the entire years measured at 10 m height in Ambo, Ethiopia.

Month	2010		2011		2012		2013		2014		2015		Average	
	V_{av}	σ												
Jan.	3.1	1.5	6.6	1.2	7.1	1.1	3.2	1.5	2.8	1.4	3.3	1.6	4.3	1.4
Feb.	3.8	1.3	7.1	0.9	7.3	1.1	3.1	0.9	2.7	1.0	2.8	1.2	4.5	1.1
Mar.	3.8	1.6	5.3	1.0	6.9	1.1	2.6	1.2	2.8	1.2	2.7	1.2	4.0	1.2
Apr	2.8	1.0	3.0	1.2	3.1	1.8	1.8	1.4	2.6	1.0	2.6	1.7	2.7	1.4
May	2.0	0.7	5.7	1.1	3.1	1.9	1.0	0.9	1.8	0.9	1.6	1.1	2.5	1.1

June	3.7	0.7	2.8	0.6	1.8	0.9	1.1	0.7	1.4	0.8	1.5	0.9	2.0	0.8
July	3.5	0.7	2.6	0.3	1.7	0.3	1.2	0.7	1.5	0.8	1.7	0.6	2.0	0.6
Aug	3.8	0.5	2.9	0.4	2.0	0.8	1.3	0.8	1.7	1.0	1.4	0.7	2.2	0.7
Sept.	5.0	0.7	4.6	0.7	1.7	0.9	1.2	0.6	1.9	0.9	1.9	1.1	2.7	0.8
Oct.	5.8	0.8	6.3	0.7	3.0	1.1	2.3	1.1	2.7	1.4	2.4	1.4	3.8	1.1
Nov.	6.3	1.2	5.9	0.7	2.3	1.1	3.1	1.4	3.9	1.4	2.2	0.8	4.0	1.1
Dec.	6.3	1.4	7.0	1.1	2.9	1.2	3.4	0.8	2.9	1.3	2.7	0.9	4.2	1.1
Av.	4.2	1.0	5.0	0.8	3.6	1.1	2.1	1.0	2.4	1.1	2.2	1.1	3.2	1.0

Wind speed is generally recorded in a time-series format. Due to the natural variability of wind, the annual energy yield of a given wind farm may change drastically from year to year depending on the wind regime of the area. Figure 1 shows monthly averaged wind speeds and their monthly variability of wind for each year. In 2010, maximum deviations were observed between the months of November to March. They are also a months with maximum wind speeds. Generally, months with minimum wind speeds also depicted minimum variations (figure 1a). In 2011, between June to November August minimum variations were recorded and the other months' variations were moderate (figure 1b). In 2012, minimum deviations were observed during the months of July, whereas the maximum occurs during April and May. The other months'

variations were moderate (figure 1c). High wind speed variations are occurred during January, April and October in 2013 and the others are moderate (figure 1d). In 2014, maximum deviations were observed between the months of October to January (figure 1e). January, April and October were a months with high wind speed variations in 2015, while minimum variations observed during the months of July and August and moderate during the other months (figure 1f).

A more elaborate pattern is observed from the average (figure 1g). During the months of January and April high wind speed variations and high wind speeds (January) and moderate (April) were observed, whereas between June to September low values of both were occurred

Figure 1: Average monthly wind speed measured at 10 m height for the years 2010 (a), 2011 (b), 2012 (c), 2013 (d), 2014 (e), 2015 (f) and average of the entire years (g), respectively

The average monthly wind speeds measured at 10 m height for each year with their average of the six years are illustrated in Figure 2. Considering averages of the entire years, high wind speeds were recorded between the months of October and March with wind speeds ranging between 3.8 to 4.5 m/s. For all other months, wind speeds were generally less than 3 m/s. Based on annual averages, 2010 and 2011 are recorded as the windiest year with the values of 4.2 m/s and 5.0 m/s, respectively. Whereas, years 2013, 2014 and 2015 had wind speeds lower than the other years. This may be due to change in wind pattern of the area or due to micro-change in the local terrain (growth of trees or building erected close to the station). In 2012 moderate annual wind speed was recorded with the value 3.6 m/s. Generally, wind speed distribution has its lowest values during the rainy months (i.e. June to September), and it peaks from the months of October and March

Figure 2: Monthly average wind speeds measured at 10 m heights for each year and their averages

4.2. Wind Data Processing

Considering the fact that rotors of the actual wind turbines are placed at heights more than 10 m and in order to choose the suitable height of the wind turbines, it is necessary to know the variations of wind speed with altitude. Extrapolating wind speed data collected at anemometric height to the required height is the first step to use these data in calculating and assessing wind energy within the designated location in the site. Thereby, the data collected at the measured 10 m height were extrapolated to 30 and 50 meter heights using Equation (3). At these heights the annual average of wind speed became 5.0 m/s and 6.2 m/s respectively, while it was only 3.2 m/s at 10 m above ground level, this corresponds to increase of, 56.25% and 93.75% respectively, from the 10 m average annual wind speed as shown in Table 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 3: Monthly average wind speed profile at 10 m and extrapolation to 30 m and 50 m.

Table 2: Monthly average mean wind speeds at 10, 30 and 50 meters.

Station	V _{av}	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Ave
Ambo	10m	4.3	4.5	4.0	2.7	2.5	2.0	2.0	2.2	2.7	3.8	4.0	4.2	3.2
	30m	6.7	7.0	6.2	4.2	3.9	3.1	3.1	3.4	4.2	5.9	6.2	6.5	5.0
	50m	8.2	8.6	7.6	5.1	4.8	3.8	3.8	4.2	5.1	7.2	7.6	8.0	6.2

For a cut-in wind speed of 4.5 m/s the turbine will be operational for 9 months of the year (September–April) and non-operational during rainy seasons of the country (June–August), the maximum operational duration is

$$\frac{9}{12} * 100\% = 75\%$$

This means the turbine will be idle or non-operational only for three months; however it can be integrated with the other sources.

4.3. Wind Speed Frequency Distribution

In this study, three numerical methods, namely Empirical Method (EM), Energy Pattern Factor method (EPF) and Maximum

Likelihood Method (MLM) are examined to estimate the Weibull parameters. To analyze the efficiency of the methods and to ascertain how closely the measured data follow the Weibull methods, statistical tests were performed using the root mean square error (RMSE) and Mean percentage error (MPE). According to the statistical test results, it can be seen that the EM followed by the EPF was the most accurate and efficient methods for determining the value of c and k to approximate wind speed distribution (Table 4). It was found that the statistical test results showed within the acceptable range for both EM and EPF methods. The MPE of EM is in the range of acceptable values between 1.31 % and 4.73 % with lowest RMSE values that ranged from 0.00029 to 0.00396. The MPE and RMSE of EPF method also found under statistically acceptable range (4.78 to 5.35 % and 0.00236 to 0.01174). Whereas,

the statistical tests rejected the MLM as an adequate method. The *MPE* of MLM is out of statistically acceptable range (-65.01 to +44.59 %) with relatively highest *RMSE* values that ranged from 0.0059 to 1.5853 (Table 4).

Using Equations (9) and (10), the monthly average and annual Weibull parameters, *k* and *c* for Ambo have been calculated for the entire years. The monthly values of Weibull shape (*k*) and scale (*c*) parameters determined using EPF method ranged from 2.19 to 3.20 with an average value of 2.80 and 2.28 to 5.02 m/s, with an average

value of 3.64 m/s, respectively. While *k* and *c* calculated using EM ranged from 2.24 to 4.99 with an average value of 3.90 and 2.19 to 4.83 m/s, with an average value of 3.54 m/s, respectively (Table 4). Even if, the statistical tests showed that EM is more accurate methods than EPF, the desired values of Weibull shape parameter (*k*) must be approach to 2. Hence, for this reason the values of *k* and *c* obtained using EPF method was considered for further discussions.

Table 3: Monthly average wind speeds and Weibull parameters at a 10 m height for the entire years studied in Ambo

Month	V _{av}	EM				EPF				MLM			
		k	c	RMSE	MPE	k	c	RMSE	MPE	k	c	RMSE	MPE
Jan.	4.34	3.84	4.76	0.00325	2.63	2.90	4.88	0.01077	4.78	7.90	3.98	0.0706	-12.24
Feb.	4.46	4.95	4.83	0.00213	2.07	3.20	5.02	0.01174	4.85	7.65	2.03	1.5853	-56.42
Mar.	4.03	3.92	4.42	0.00310	2.76	2.95	4.53	0.00931	4.78	6.33	3.16	0.2629	-25.43
Apr.	2.66	2.24	2.97	0.00396	4.73	2.28	2.99	0.00474	5.17	2.72	4.12	0.3519	44.59
May	2.53	2.65	2.78	0.00099	2.49	2.19	2.84	0.00456	5.35	3.26	2.87	0.0059	6.07
June	2.03	3.10	2.24	0.00071	2.62	2.45	2.29	0.00254	4.95	3.69	1.27	0.1802	-41.73
July	2.03	4.99	2.19	0.00052	2.26	3.02	2.28	0.00236	4.80	7.40	0.74	0.4334	-65.01
Aug	2.17	3.87	2.36	0.00029	1.58	2.71	2.44	0.00272	4.80	3.19	1.12	0.3165	-51.74
Sept.	2.73	3.92	2.97	0.00067	1.90	2.77	3.06	0.00425	4.78	2.60	1.47	0.4564	-49.55
Oct.	3.77	4.41	4.06	0.00061	1.31	2.88	4.23	0.00810	4.78	3.75	2.55	0.4738	-36.55
Nov.	3.95	4.58	4.30	0.00236	2.46	3.09	4.44	0.00905	4.81	4.56	2.46	0.6734	-41.54
Dec.	4.19	4.33	4.58	0.00299	2.61	3.17	4.71	0.01031	4.84	5.41	2.64	0.7229	-40.55
Av.	3.24	3.90	3.54	0.00180	2.45	2.80	3.64	0.00670	4.89	4.87	2.37	0.4611	-30.84

Figure 4 shows the probability density function (PDF) for the study area. The wind speed tends to distribute around the mean value most of the time. The distribution in Ambo is spread and high frequency is not observed at low wind speeds because the shape factor is relatively high. This reveals the wind potential of the area to be good. Figure 5 shows the cumulative density function (CDF) for the study area. It tells the probability that the wind speed is less than a given value. A wind speed smaller than the turbine cut-in speed (4.5m/s) has a probability of occurrence of 25 % of the time.

average wind power is proportional to hub height.

Figure 4: Probability distribution function of the annual wind speed.

Figure 6: Average monthly Wind Power density at 10, 30 and 50 m heights

The average wind power density shown in Figure 6 is calculated using wind speed at 30m and 50 m heights for Ambo area. Air density of 1.225 kg/m³ was assumed to calculate power density at a height of 30 and 50 m. Figure 6 has similar trend with the mean wind speed shown in Figure 3. Since wind power density is proportional to the cube of wind speed, a small variation on wind speed will lead to a significant variation in wind power density. With these computed wind power estimates, an attempt has next been made to divide approximately the various wind classes based on ‘International Wind Power Classification’ (shown in Table 6).

Figure 5: Cumulative distribution function of the annual mean wind speed

4.4. Wind power density Analysis

Using Equation (13), we can calculate the monthly average wind power per unit cross sectional area of a turbine. Thereby, this entity was estimated for wind power extracted at different heights: 10 m, 30 m and 50 m as shown in Table 5 and Figure 6. As expected Table 4: Monthly average Wind power density (W/m²) at 10, 30 and 50 m heights.)

Heights	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Ave
10 m	48.7	55.8	39.2	12.1	9.6	4.9	4.9	6.5	12.1	33.6	39.2	45.4	26.0
30 m	184.2	210.1	146.0	45.4	36.3	18.2	18.2	24.1	45.4	125.8	146.0	168.2	97.3
50 m	337.7	389.6	268.9	81.2	67.7	33.6	33.6	45.4	81.2	228.6	268.9	313.6	179.2

Table 5: International Wind Power Classification

Class	Resource Potential	30 m Height		50 m Height	
		Wind Speed (m/s)	Wind Power(W/m ²)	Wind Speed (m/s)	Wind Power(W/m ²)
1	Poor	0 – 5.1	0 – 160	0 – 5.6	0 – 200
2	Marginal	5.1 – 5.9	160 – 240	5.6 – 6.4	200 – 300
3	Moderate	5.9 – 6.5	240 – 320	6.4 – 7.0	300 – 400
4	Good	6.5 – 7.0	320 – 400	7.0 – 7.5	400 – 500
5	Excellent	7.0 – 7.4	400 – 480	7.5 – 8.0	500 – 600
6	Outstanding	7.4 – 8.2	480 – 640	8.0 – 8.8	600 – 800
7	Superb	8.2 – 11.0	640 – 1600	8.8 – 11.9	800 – 2000

Source: Wind Power Classification of the US Department of Energy (DOE).

Table 6: Monthly and annual energy density at 10, 30 and 50 m heights.

Height s	kWh/m ² /month												kWh/m ² /year
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	
10 m	36.2	37.5	29.2	8.7	7.1	3.5	3.6	4.9	8.7	25.0	28.2	33.8	227.7
30 m	137.1	141.2	108.6	32.7	27.0	13.1	13.6	17.9	32.7	93.6	105.1	125.1	852.6
50 m	251.3	261.8	200.0	58.5	50.4	24.2	25.0	33.8	58.5	170.1	193.6	233.3	1569.6

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: (a) Monthly and (b) annual energy density at 10, 30 and 50 m heights.

According to the standard of 'International Wind Power Classification' (shown in Table 6), Ambo area falls under 'Class 2' and is classified as 'Marginal' for most times of the year. It has average wind power density of 179.2 W/m² at 50 m height.

4.5. Monthly and Annual Energy Density Calculations

The monthly average and yearly wind energy per unit cross sectional area of a turbine was calculated using equation (14) and (15). Thereby, this entity was estimated for wind energy extracted at different heights: 10 m, 30 m and 50 m as shown in Table 7. As expected mean wind energy is proportional to hub height. At 30 m and 50 m heights the annual average of wind energy density became 852.6 kWh/m² and 1569.6 kWh/m² respectively, while it was only

227.7 kWh/m² at 10 m, this corresponds to more than 3.5 and 6.5 times that of obtained at 10 m height, respectively (Figure 7).

5. Conclusions

The aim of this study was to assess the potential of wind power in Ambo, West Shewa Zone of Oromia Region, Ethiopia. Monthly average wind speed data of Ambo during the period of 2010-2015 have been statistically analyzed. The most important outcomes of this study can be summarized as follows:

- ❖ Long term seasonal wind speeds were found that the windiest months were during the period from November to March, while the calmest months were from June to August. The maximum monthly Average wind speeds are recorded as 4.5 m/s in

February and the minimum values are recorded as 2.0 m/s in June and July at 10 m height.

- ❖ Average wind speed measured at 10 m height is determined as 3.2 m/s for the studied period. This speed increases by, respectively 56.25% and 93.75%, when it is extrapolated to 30 m and 50 m hub height.
- ❖ The wind energy potential in Ambo area is quite promising, because the wind speed range for electricity generation is within 5 - 6 m/s at 10 m height, therefore, the site studied is not suitable for electric wind application in large-scale ($v_{av}=3.2$ m/s at 10 m).
- ❖ The Average annual value of Weibull shape parameter k is 2.80, while the annual value of the scale parameter c is 3.64 m/s.
- ❖ The average monthly and yearly wind power density and energy density was estimated at different heights: 10 m, 30 m and 50 m. The yearly average wind power density values ranged from 33.6 to 389.6 W/m² at 50 m heights, this level of power density may be adequate for non-grid connected electrical and mechanical applications, such as wind generators, battery charging and water pumping as well as agricultural applications.
- ❖ At the end the present work is only preliminary study in order to assess wind energy potential of Ambo, Western Shewa of Oromia region and give useful insights to engineers and experts dealing with wind energy.

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